
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE:

SUSTAINABILITY ISSUES & CHALLENGES IN TOURISM

3-5 October 2013, Istanbul, Turkey

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INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE:
SUSTAINABILITY ISSUES
&
CHALLENGES IN TOURISM

3-5 October 2013, Istanbul, Turkey

Serhat Adem SOP

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Foreword

On behalf of the organizing committee, it is our pleasure to welcome you to the international conference on Sustainability Issues and Challenges in Tourism hosted by Boğaziçi University and New Buckinghamshire University. This event will take place in Istanbul, Turkey, at Boğaziçi University between October 3 and October 5, 2013. The conference is aimed at providing a forum for academicians and practitioners to share and discuss ideas and to identify the challenges that sustainable tourism poses.

Sustainability as a concept has been used in multitude of settings, and many and distinct definitions of the term have emerged. However, sustainability is generally thought to encompass different dimensions that include economic, environmental and socio-cultural, and tourism development needs to be considered within a long-term perspective that encompasses the well-being of both current and future generations. Within this perspective, the theme of the conference focuses on the issues and challenges that destinations and businesses alike face when trying to adopt sustainability as an operating philosophy.

The articles in this proceedings book include a wide collection of both research studies and conceptual papers that address the topic from many different perspectives. It is our hope that during the conference many and interrelated issues are identified and sound solutions to the problems are posed.

We would like to express our gratitude to the members of the organizing committee who have spent countless hours putting this conference together. Additionally, we also thank the international scientific committee and the reviewers, who have worked to ensure the quality of the submitted papers.

On behalf of the organizing committee, we would like to welcome you again to the conference. We hope that you will be able to enjoy the Turkish hospitality during the conference and that you will have an unforgettable stay in Istanbul.

Maria D. ALVAREZ
Boğaziçi University
Conference Co-Chair

Eugenia WICKENS
Help to Educate Foundation
Conference Co-Chair

Ali BAKİR
New Buckinghamshire University
Conference Co-Chair

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- Medet Yolal – *Anadolu University, Turkey*

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Emotional dissonance and customer satisfaction: An unexpected relationship in disabled tourism market

Burhan KILIÇ

Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University, Turkey, bkilic@mu.edu.tr

Merve BAŞ

Maltepe University, Turkey, mervebas@maltepe.edu.tr

and

Serhat Adem SÖP***

Mehmet Akif Ersoy University, Turkey, sa_sop@yahoo.com

Abstract

When customer satisfaction is considered as the target for those organizations, expecting a smiley and happy face (etc.) from the employees become one of the unwritten rules in tourism organizations. In this process, emotional dissonance may be felt by the employees who try to display the emotions desired by the organizations. After a certain time, this situation can bring some problems such as emotional exhaustion, alienation and negative thinking. So, it has been thought that there is a negatively directed relationship between emotional dissonance perception and satisfaction level of disabled holidaymakers. Nonetheless, the positively directed relationship which was explained with 14.1% between perceived emotional dissonance and disabled holidaymakers' satisfaction was determined according to the results of the correlation analysis. This means, when the level of emotional dissonance increases, the satisfaction level of disabled holidaymakers also grows. As a different consequence from the studies seen in the literature, this may be caused due to the delicate structure of disabled market. The reason of this direct proportion can be thought as the employees are satisfied with their jobs and they serve to a different group that consists of disabled individuals.

Keywords: Disabled market, disabled holidaymakers, emotional dissonance and customer satisfaction.

Introduction

When the participation right to tourism activities is considered, the existence of a tourism industry supplying equal opportunities for everyone is understood as a necessity. Thus, in tourism activities the disabled guests must be cared as much as the others, maybe more. So, the term *disabled tourism* arises with those disabled individuals who are travelling, having accommodation and participating in tourism activities. There are more than 650 million disabled individuals in the world and these people need to be encouraged for participation in tourism activities. With respect to this, disabled tourism market can become widespread and the dynamism in economic, social and cultural aspects will be seen.

Occasionally, the organizations ask their employees to exhibit some emotions which they are not actually feeling at that moment. In this situation, a conflict or an inconsistency which occurs because of the contrast between the actual feelings and exhibited ones can be observed (Morris and Feldman, 1996: 992). This process which is explained as *emotional dissonance* is highly seen in service sector, especially in tourism. Since, customer satisfaction is placed in the main purposes of tourism organizations and the difference between perceived quality and expectations affects the satisfaction level. When customer satisfaction is considered as the target for those organizations, expecting a smiley and happy face (etc.) from the employees become one of the unwritten rules in tourism organizations. When considered in terms of disabled market, it is observed that emotional dissonance and customer satisfaction relationship becomes more sensitive.

For the purpose of this study, two dimensions of emotional labor (emotional effort and emotional dissonance) have been examined in disabled market, firstly. However, the results of the relationship between emotional dissonance and customer satisfaction have been realized as contrast to the literature. Therefore, only the relationship between emotional dissonance and customer satisfaction has been studied in this study and this relationship has been investigated with questionnaires performed on disabled holidaymakers who paid for tourism service. The reasons for selecting disabled market as the research area are; being quiet new in tourism sector and scarce academic investigations on this field. Hence, it is expected that the findings of this study will make contribution to both future academic researches and managers in tourism sector.

Literature Review

Emotional Dissonance

Emotional dissonance is the difference between the expected emotional display from the employee and the emotional display that the employee is willing to do (Çukur ve Şahin, 2007: 487). According to Morris and Feldman (1996: 992), emotional dissonance is the conflict or inconsistency between the real and the exhibited emotions of the employee. As understood, emotional dissonance is occurred when the organization asks the employee to exhibit his/her unreal emotions. In that case, it should be mentioned that if the employee's emotional dissonance level increases, the need of emotional labor will also increase (Öz, 2007: 9).

Hochschild (1983:7) describes emotional labor as the management of emotions to create images which reflect the face and the body as observed from the outside. Other description belongs to Morris and Feldman (1996: 987) is defined as the effort, planning

and control of emotional display during the interpersonal relation that asked by the organization. According to Diefendorff and Richard (2003: 284), emotional labor can be described as the management of emotions as a part of business role.

The organizations pay a salary to the employee not only for work effort but also for a smile and a good representation of the organization. Based on this idea, the employee can be described as "actor or actress", the organization as "scene" and the customer as "audience". According to the managers of the organizations, being cheerful, constructive and helpful by the employee affects customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in a positive way. These positive attitudes of the employee are in direct proportional to their emotional labor achievements (Chu and Murrman, 2006: 1181; Hochschild, 1983: 334).

Although the employee that controls his/her emotions lives emotional dissonance, he/she displays emotional effort for both orienting him/her to the display rules of the workplace and trying to exhibit the right emotions asked by the organization. So, emotional effort represents the employee's struggle for fulfilling the rules set by the organization. Generally, it is thought that emotional effort should be performed when the organization asks the employee exhibit different kinds of emotions (Öz, 2007: 8). In such cases where emotional dissonance happens, it is expected that more emotional effort should be performed to respond the emotions desired by the organization (Kruml and Geddes, 2000: 177-188).

From time to time, emotional display that desired by the organization can cause hiding the natural emotions of the employee. For example, a salesperson can feel that the product which he sells is insufficient. However, he promotes the product because his job requires it. After a certain time, this situation can bring some problems such as emotional exhaustion, alienation and negative thinking (Güngör, 2009: 174). In spite of this, according to the study of Bakker and Heuven (2006: 436) that carried out with 101 police officers and 108 nurses, the nurses observed the alleviation of patients' sufferings due to their smiling faces to the patients. Additionally, the nurses mentioned that they didn't feel emotional exhaustion, alienation or negative thinking that arises as a result of emotional dissonance.

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is explained with lots of definitions in the literature. Oliver (1997) defines the term as a pleasant satisfactoriness judgment on consumption of a product or a service. According to Kotler et al. (2002: 8), customer satisfaction occurs when perceived quality and customers' expectations are matched. Similarly, Bitner and Zeithaml (2003) stated that satisfaction is the customers' evaluation of a product or service in terms of whether the product or service has met their needs and expectations. As seen, if the perceived quality meets customer expectations, customer satisfaction is achieved. Thus, matching customer's expectation and the perceived quality is the basic goal for the organizations to create customer satisfaction. In order achieve this goal, the organizations should focus on understanding the expectations of their customers and respond them actively in this way (Kotler et al., 2002: 8).

Figure 1. Customer satisfaction based cycle

Source: McAlexander, Kaldenburg and Koenig (1994).

Customer satisfaction, profitability and service quality are the items of an important cycle. In this context, the basic requirement to create customer loyalty or commitment is the customer satisfaction itself. In addition, customer satisfaction has a positive impact on profitability and the market share (Meng and Elliot, 2009: 56). As seen on figure 1, reaching customer satisfaction creates loyalty and this increases the level of profitability which means an opportunity to create pecuniary resource that increases the level of service quality in the organization.

Disabled Tourism

American laws explain disability as the mental and physical obstacles that limits the individual's vital activity (Çakmak , 2008: 56). According to the definition of Administration for Disabled Individuals (in Turkish Republic), a disabled individual is someone who has lost his/her physical, mental, spiritual, emotional and social skills in varying degrees because of an illness/accident or a congenital situation that makes him/her unable to perform some of the requirements of the normal life. Different from the others, World Tourism Organization (UNTWO) defines disabled individual as the person who has physical, mental or sensory disabilities that suffers due some relational problems and needs special care in travel, accommodation and other tourism services (unwto.org).

In 1975, Education for All Handicapped Children Act (EHA) which was one of the most important legal regulations so far was accepted in the United States. This act classified disabilities as "mental retardation, emotional disturbance, learning disabilities,

visual, and hearing impairments, paraphrasia, deafness, blindness, other health impairments and multiple disabilities" (Simpson and Warner, 2010:1).

When the participation right to tourism activities is considered, the existence of a tourism industry supplying equal opportunities for everyone is understood as a necessity. Thus, in tourism activities the disabled guests must be cared as much as the others, maybe more. As stated in the United Nations Human Rights Congress, there are more than 650 million disabled individuals in the world and these individuals should be encouraged for participation in tourism activities. Thus, disabled tourism will grow when those individuals become travellers, hotel guests and participants in different tourism activities (unescap.org).

Disabled tourism can be evaluated as a sub-branch of *medical tourism* as seen in third age tourism. In this case, the elderly tourist whose body health is not fully good may be evaluated in the context of disabled tourism. So, a holiday for an elderly tourist that is in the age group of 65 and more is evaluated in both health tourism and disabled tourism (Aydın vd., 2011: 6). 80 million disabled individuals live in European Union countries and this number represents one-sixth of the total European population (ec.europa.eu). According to the researches carried out in 2009, there were 105.4 million disabled individuals (aged more than 18) in the USA (cdc.gov). The numbers in Turkey show that 12,29 % of the whole population consists of disabled individuals (www.candaozurolmaz.org). Besides, the number of disabled individuals who participate in tourism activities is still not clear in Turkey.

Disabled holidaymakers who seek extra care may need private companions (could be a family member or a friend) and special activities. This situation of need generates *care tourism*. The companion will help disabled holidaymakers not only in transportation but also in all travel and shopping activities during their holiday periods. On the other hand, the companion may need a companion, too. Then, an employee of the tourism organization will stand by the companions who make holiday with disabled holidaymakers (Vos and Ivor, 2008: 17).

Some foundations like UNWTO, ENAT (European Network Accessible Tourism) and Fundacion ONCE have arranged a number of important conferences to develop disabled tourism in the world and have taken some decisions as listed below:

- UNWTO arranged a conference in Madrid, in 1991. Some supportive decisions on accessibility and attractiveness subjects in disabled tourism were taken in this conference (unwto.org).
- In addition to the meeting arranged in 1991, UNWTO took new decisions in 2005. Some of the precautions taken in the conference were about providing the private parking areas for disabled individuals, training the hotel employees in the context of disabled tourism and arranging public places suitable for disabled holidaymakers (unwto.org).
- UNWTO, ENAT and Fundacion ONCE foundations planned to sign an agreement in 2011. It was about protecting the rights of disabled individuals, increasing accessibility and improving quality of life for the disabled ones (accessibletourism.org).

Methodology

The disabled individuals that have participated in tourism activities in Turkey constitute the population and sample of this study. The sample of the study consists of 340 disabled holidaymakers that have been selected randomly. The tested hypothesis is "there is a negatively directed relationship between emotional dissonance perception and satisfaction level of disabled holidaymakers".

In order to specify the statements of emotional dissonance, the scale HELS (Hospitality Emotional Labor Scale) that was developed by Chu and Murman (2006) has been used. Firstly, the terms in the scale have been translated into Turkish. Then, the terms in the scale have been tested if they are understandable or not by implementing on 30 college students. Finally, it has been determined that the terms in the scale are understandable and so, the emotional dissonance part of the questionnaire form has been completed. In the process of establishing whole questionnaire form, the studies in relation to the subject (Ashfort and Humphrey, 1993; Morris and Feldman, 1996; Grandey, 2000; Gardner et al., 2009; Chu and Murrman, 2006; Güngör, 2009) have been reviewed and it has been consulted with experts about the questionnaire form.

So as to reach disabled individuals in the research stage (eight-month period between September 2011 and April 2012); rehabilitation centers, associations, training centers and sports clubs for disabled individuals have been benefited. 37 disabled individuals have been surveyed on the internet and totally 340 questionnaire forms have been collected (315 of them have been determined as usable).

There have been 11 statements on the questionnaire form to determine emotional dissonance level and 5 statements for measuring satisfaction about the enterprises that the disabled holidaymakers lodged. Besides, some descriptive questions about gender, age, marital status, education level, disability level, the average holiday budget, the frequency of making holiday in a year and the motivation for lodging in tourism enterprises have been added to the questionnaire form.

In emotional dissonance dimension, the first 9 statements of 11 have been encoded inversely. According to the results, 4 statements have been removed due to the low reliability scores: 1) "the employees are acting like in a good mood when dealing with disabled guests" 2) "the employees are displaying the same emotions they feel while serving disabled guests" 3) "the employees are actually feeling their behaviors that are exhibited to be able to serve better to disabled guests" 4) "the employees are reflecting the emotions that they feel against the disabled guests".

This time in satisfaction dimension, 2 statements have been encoded inversely as 1) "my experience that I have got in the enterprise which I have preferred is not a pleasant one" 2) "I regret that I have come to the enterprise which I have preferred". On the other hand, the statement "my experience that I have got in the enterprise which I have preferred is not a pleasant one" has been removed due to the low reliability scores.

Construct validity of the scale has been confirmed with the results and it has been determined that factor analysis has been able to

emotional dissonance levels by disabled guests and their satisfaction levels. In accordance with the results of the conducted correlation analysis, there was a positively directed relationship (explained with 14.1%) between emotional dissonance and customer satisfaction ($r=0.141$; $p=0.013<0.05$). In this situation it is understood that as the level of emotional dissonance increases, the satisfaction level of disabled guests also increases. Therefore, the hypothesis "there is a negatively directed relationship between emotional dissonance perception and satisfaction level of disabled holidaymakers" has not been supported.

Table 3: The Results of the Correlation Analysis between Emotional Dissonance and Customer Satisfaction

		Emotional Dissonance	Customer Satisfaction
Emotional Dissonance	r	1,000	0,141
	p	0,000	0,013*
	n	315	315
Customer Satisfaction	r	0,141	1,000
	p	0,013*	0,000
	n	315	315

* $p < 0,05$

Conclusion and Discussion

The literature review proves that emotional dissonance that is lived by the employee causes emotional exhaustion and alienation. As a matter of course, this situation decreases the level of job satisfaction for employees and finally decreases the level of customer satisfaction, too (Botheridge and Grandey, 2002; Chu and Murrman, 2006; Johnson, 2007; Güngör, 2009). Conversely in this study, the positively directed relationship that is explained with 14.1% between perceived emotional dissonance and disabled holidaymakers' satisfaction has been determined. It means, when the level of emotional dissonance increases, the satisfaction level of disabled guests also grows. This different consequence from the studies seen in the literature is caused due to the disabled market. The reason of this direct proportion can be thought as the employees are satisfied with their jobs and they serve to a different group that consists of disabled individuals.

According to the results of this study, some suggestions can be listed. First of all, in order not to face the negative results of emotional dissonance like emotional exhaustion and alienation, some kind of methods such as rewarding, job rotation and providing technical support should be used to increase the level of employees' motivation. Besides, the employees should be chosen carefully for some departments where face to face communications are seen (like food and beverage, front office and animation). So, the employees should be the ones who are able to exhibit emotional effort against disabled guests and always try to make these guests satisfied with the service.

With reference to the results of the study, 18-29 aged disabled guests evaluate emotional dissonance of the employees more than the other age groups. Thus, the employees should exhibit their emotions professionally to this age group of disabled guests. It is also important to train the employees for exhibiting emotions and behaving to disabled guests. They should also be informed about the importance of being patient, lenient and helpful.

So as to be successful in disabled tourism market, the tourism enterprises should make a point of the extents of reception desks, decorations of the rooms, entrances and exits of the hotels, rooms and even parking lots etc. Making technical regulations by using appropriate measurements is another key point in this process. For example, if a ramp to the entrance of the hotel has not been measured correctly, this mistake will make it impossible for disabled guests to use the ramp. Managers of these enterprises should also be more sensitive against this issue.

Apart from all these applications, it should be noted that the disabled guests need to feel in holiday mood, not in a rehabilitation center. Although making holiday requires a little bit more budget for disabled individuals, these holidaymakers are willing to spend more for an extra care. So, the managers of the enterprises should be aware of the risk as if disabled individuals do not feel that they find private care in the enterprises, they may give up making holiday or may not rely on the enterprises (Broeder, 2007).

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